

ANALYTICAL APPLICATIONS OF DUTOIT'S THERMOVOLUMETRY.
PART II. ANALYSIS OF ZINC IN BRASS

By KUMAR KRISHNA CHATTERJI

The thermometric method has been applied in the estimation of Cu and Zn by titration with $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Hg}(\text{CNS})_4$. Zn in presence of Cu and in brass has been estimated using the same reagent after removing Cu from the solution as $\text{Cu}_2(\text{CNS})_2$ by adding NH_4CNS and H_2SO_4 . The method provides results for Zn which are usually + 1% higher than those obtained by gravimetric estimation as NH_4ZnPO_4 .

In Part I of this series (Chatterji, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 366) a method for the rapid analysis of Ca and Mg in Dolomite, based on a modification of the thermometric titration of Dutoit (*J. chim. phys.*, 1922, 19, 324, 331), was described. The same method has been extended to the analysis of brass in the present communication. Although attempt has been made to develop a quick method for the determination of both Cu and Zn in brass, it has been possible so far to apply the method for the estimation of zinc only.

Of the different reagents that were tried, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Hg}(\text{CNS})_4$ was found to suit the purpose well. This reagent affords insoluble precipitates with both Cu and Zn with sufficient heat change and is thus not specific, but it precipitates none of the other metals present in brass under the condition of the titration. The reagent has, however, one disadvantage. The precipitates of the corresponding Cu and Zn compounds appear slowly due to supersaturation phenomenon. Hence, during the thermometric titration a longer time (2 minutes) has to be allowed for attainment of a constant temperature, and the rate of stirring should also be somewhat more vigorous. For the estimation of Cu and Zn in a mixture, the following procedure was found expedient. First of all the total Cu and Zn was titrated thermometrically against a standard $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Hg}(\text{CNS})_4$ solution. In an aliquot Cu was precipitated as $\text{Cu}_2(\text{CNS})_2$ by adding NH_4CNS in presence of H_2SO_4 . Zn remaining in the solution was then titrated with the same titrant, as before. It should be pointed out that the above procedure did not permit the determination of total Cu and Zn in cases (e.g. brass) where Cu:Zn ratio was wide enough. In the latter cases the corresponding thermometric diagram shows a pronounced curvature near the end-point, which could not therefore be correctly ascertained by the graphical method. However, after removal of Cu as $\text{Cu}_2(\text{CNS})_2$, Zn could be determined with accuracy.

EXPERIMENTAL

The standard and stock solutions were prepared in the following way: 0.4 M $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Hg}(\text{CNS})_4$ solution was prepared as usual by dissolving HgCl_2 in NH_4SCN solution. The strengths of the prepared solutions of ZnSO_4 and CuSO_4 , as obtained from the determination of Zn as ZnNH_4PO_4 and Cu iodometrically, were respectively 0.1042M

and 0.1015M. Zn in brass was determined according to the procedure described by Vogel ("Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 2nd ed., p. 559).

The thermometric apparatus is the same as that described earlier by the author (*loc. cit.*)

In the thermometric titrations of pure CuSO_4 and ZnSO_4 solutions at different concentrations (prepared by dilution of the stock solutions) 50 c.c. of the solution was taken in the Dewar. A few drops of dilute acetic acid were added, and titration was done as usual with 0.4M- $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Hg}(\text{CNS})_4$ solution, adding 1 c.c. of the reagent at a time. As the heat change took place slowly, the rate of stirring was increased and intervals of 2 minutes were allowed between two successive additions of the titre, during which the temperature attained a constant value.

A similar procedure was employed for mixtures of Cu and Zn sulphate solutions. For the titration of Zn alone in the mixture, Cu was precipitated, as mentioned above, by adding to the mixture in the Dewar 5 c.c. of a fresh saturated solution of SO_2 in water and 10 c.c. of a 20% solution of NH_4SCN . The system was allowed to equilibrate for one hour before titration.

The following method is proposed for the thermometric estimation of Zn in a sample of brass.

About 3 g. of brass is dissolved in 30-40 c.c. of HNO_3 (1:1) and the solution evaporated with a few c.c. of H_2SO_4 (conc.) till HNO_3 is completely removed. The residue is taken up with water, filtered and free acid cautiously neutralised with ammonia (1:1). To the solution is added 10 c.c. of a 25% solution of sodium acetate, followed by 2 c.c. of glacial acetic acid, which brings the p_n of the solution around 4.0, when diluted to 250 c.c. in a volumetric flask. An aliquot of the solution (50 c.c.) is taken in the Dewar and Cu precipitated according to the procedure described above. In the residual solution Zn is titrated as before with 0.4 M $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Hg}(\text{CNS})_4$.

The results of the thermometric titrations and those by other methods have been summarised in Tables I-IV for comparison.

TABLE I

CuSO_4 with $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Hg}(\text{CNS})_4$.			
	Curve a.	Curve b.	Curve c.
End-points (in c.c.)	13.0	6.55	5.25
Cu (found thermometrically in g.)	0.3307	0.1665	0.1336
Cu (found iodometrically in g.)	0.3313	0.1657	0.1325
% Error in thermometry	-0.2	+0.5	+0.8

TABLE II

ZnSO_4 with $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Hg}(\text{CNS})_4$.			
	Curve a.	Curve b.	Curve c.
End-points (in c.c.)	12.7	6.3	5.1
Zn (found thermometrically in g.)	0.3321	0.1654	0.1334
Zn (found gravimetrically in g.)	0.3317	0.1659	0.1327
% Error in thermometry	+0.12	-0.3	+0.54

TABLE III

Zn in mixtures of $ZnSO_4$ and $CuSO_4$ solutions with $(NH_4)_2Hg(CNS)_4$.

	Curve a.	Curve b.
End-points (in c.c.)	6.4	5.1
Zn (found thermometrically in g.)	0.1674	0.1334
Zn (found gravimetrically in g.)	0.1659	0.1327
% Error in thermometry	+0.9	+0.54

TABLE IV

Zn in brass with $(NH_4)_2Hg(CNS)_4$.

	Curve a.	Curve b.
End-points (in c.c.)	8.05	6.8
Zn (found thermometrically in g.)	35.74	30.45
Zn (found gravimetrically in g.)	35.45	30.15
% Error in thermometry	+1.0	+1.0

FIG. 3

The thermometric diagrams have been drawn by plotting the corrected temperatures (cf. Chatterji, *loc. cit.*) ΔT_{cv} against the volume of the titre added.

Here
$$\Delta T_{ov} = \frac{\Delta T (V + dv)}{V}$$

where ΔT = observed temperature change in $^{\circ}$ arising out of the addition of dv c.c. of titre to V c.c. of the system in the Dewar.

DISCUSSION

From Tables I-IV and Figs. 1-4 it is clear that in the individual estimation of Cu and Zn and of Zn in Cu-Zn mixtures and brass, agreement is within 1% between values obtained by the thermometric and the chemical methods. The concentrations of the solutions used lie between $M/10$ and $M/30$. In the case of Zn, the thermometric method is especially recommended, as a suitable volumetric method for its estimation is still lacking.

The non-rectilinear nature of the thermometric diagram obtained in the titration of total Cu and Zn in mixtures (Fig. 3) is readily explained if we recognise the

FIG. 4

fact that during the first part of the titration of the mixture, there is coprecipitation of $ZnHg(CNS)_4$ and $CuHg(CNS)_4$, but during the later part of the operation either pure $ZnHg(CNS)_4$ or pure $CuHg(CNS)_4$ is precipitated according as Zn or Cu is present in excess in the mixture. These considerations are directly supported by the fact that as the ratios of $Cu^{++} : Zn^{++}$ in the mixtures are varied, the resulting thermometric diagrams deviate more and more from the straight line course (Fig. 3).

The method of analysis of Zn in brass, proposed in this paper, provides results which are 1% higher than the values obtained by analysing as $Zn_2P_2O_7$. In the latter, the low result is not unlikely owing to the slight solubility of $ZnNH_4PO_4$ and consequent loss in weight during washing. Referred to the gravimetric result as the standard, the thermometric result therefore will be less by about 1%.

DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA-9.

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